

SOP Scanning Electron Microscopy of environmental microplastics.

1. Introduction and Scope

The main purpose of this imaging analysis is to evaluate microorganisms' adherence, biofilm formation, and surface morphology of microplastics recovered from water samples via Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). Based on the observed microbial presence, the micrographies generated will inform which samples should be further studied via Fluorescence In-Situ Hybridisation.

2. Principle of the Method

As described in the SOP "Water Column Filtration and Storage", at each sampling location, 100 L – 400 L of water will be filtered, resulting in a concentrate at the cod end of approx. 50 mL. The concentrate will be first split into two fractions (a and b, 25 mL each), both of which will be filtered onto Nylon filters (NFs, pore size 45 μ m). Collected MPs will be subject of two major different analysis: a) DNA extraction and b) Imaging (Scanning Electron Microscopy, SEM and Fluorescence In-Situ Hybridisation FISH), and as such filters need to be processed and stored differentially, in an appropriate way for subsequent analysis. This SOP describes the protocol to process NFs filters for SEM.

3. Chemicals and Reagents

- 70% Ethanol (EtOH) for sterilisation of equipment.
- 0.2 M Phosphate Buffer Saline (PBS)
- 2.5% (w/v) glutaraldehyde (GA)
- PBS [0.2M] / EtOH [100% v/v] 50:50 v/v
- EtOH high purity grade 50% v/v, 70% v/v, 80% v/v, 90% v/v, 100% v/v

4. Materials and Equipment

- Nylon filters (45 μ m pore size, ϕ 47 mm)
- Flat tip tweezers
- Gloves
- Falcon tubes (50 mL) for concentrate storage
- Falcon tubes (15 mL) for filter storage
- Gloves

5. Method for microplastics preparation for SEM

5.1 Filters fixation

- 5.1.1 Following antiseptic techniques and immediately after vacuum filtration, the NF for MPs imaging analyses (SEM and FISH) will be stored in a Falcon tube containing enough GA (2.5 % v/v) to cover the filter (approx. 4 mL) for 2 h.
- 5.1.2 Depending on the accessibility to a freeze dryer, imaging filters can be either dehydrated (step 5.2.5) or be transferred from GA, into fresh tubes and stored in 50:50 EtOH 100 % v/v and PBS (0.2 M) and keep at – 20 C.

5.2 Filters dehydration

- 5.2.1 Filters will be transferred into PBS (0.2 M) and placed in fresh Falcon tubes with EtOH 50 % v/v. After 10 mins, the EtOH will be discarded and replaced with EtOH 70 % v/v. Following 10 mins more, the EtOH solution will be again discarded and replaced with EtOH 80% v/v, and then 90% v/v. After 10 mins more the solution will be replaced with EtOH 100%. The last dehydration step (EtOH 100% v/v) will be repeated twice.

5.3 SEM

- 5.3.1 After the EtOH gradient, filters will be transferred into Petri dishes and placed inside a freeze dryer for 24 h.
- 5.3.2 Cut-outs of the filters will be mounted on aluminium stubs, and sputter coated with gold palladium before observing with a field emission scanning electron microscope.
- 5.3.3 The resulting micrographs will be inspected for microorganisms' adherence, biofilm formation, and surface morphology of microplastics. These images will inform which filters can be further studied via Fluorescence In-Situ Hybridisation.

6 Documentation

Clear labelling of the Petri dishes and micrography files will be required. The labels need to include location, depth, and date of collection.

7 Safety

Researchers have undertaken a Health and Safety lab induction.

8 References

[Carrillo-Barragan P., 2022, SOP Water column collection, filtration, and sample storage for microbiological analyses of microplastics](#)

[Qiang L., et al., 2021, Environ. Sci. Technol. 2021, 55, 16402–16412. DOI: 10.1021/acs.est.1c04108](#)

[Shlundt et al., 2019, Mol Ecol Resour. 2020;20:620–634, DOI: 10.1111/1755-0998.13119](#)